

Evaluation of cytoplasmic male sterile and maintainer lines in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated 18 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) A lines (Table 1) and their corresponding maintainers (B lines) in

1993 wet season (WS) at CLRRI. The A lines were planted in two rows and the B lines in four rows, with 25 plants per row. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 2-cm spacing. We evaluated A lines for pollen and spikelet sterility, panicle exertion, and flag leaf length and width. Panicle length, grains/panicle, and grain shape were recorded for B lines. Days to 50% flowering, plant height, panicles/plant and disease reaction were recorded for both A and B lines. To determine

pollen sterility, we collected five florets from five plants before flowering; pollen grains were stained with KI. Spikelet sterility was recorded for five panicles (bagged before emergence) from five plants. Other traits were recorded for five randomly selected plants.

CMS and maintainer lines were evaluated for field reaction to ragged stunt virus and agronomic characteristics (Table 2).

IR62829 A had spikelet fertility of 2% and IR58025 A of 5% in this experiment (Table 1), although in previous seasons at CLRRI, they showed complete pollen and spikelet sterility.

CMS lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A are being used to develop F₁ hybrids for multilocation yield testing in Vietnam. Based on these results, however, CMS and maintainer lines of IR58025, IR62829, and IR64608 must be purified using the pair crossing method. CMS lines IR66707 A, Pragathi A, Madhuri A, PMS8 A, and PMS10 A have good agronomic traits and are suitable for use in the Cuu Long Delta. ■

Table 1. Characteristics of CMS lines in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam. 1993 WS.

CMS line	CMS source	Origin	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Panicle exertion (scale)	Flag leaf (cm)	
						Length	Width
IR58025 A	WA ^a	IRRI	95	95	7	30.7	1.5
IR62829 A	WA	IRRI	95	98	5	28.5	1.0
IR64608 A	WA	IRRI	97	99	7	31.0	1.7
IR67684 A	WA	IRRI	100	100	7	19.0	1.3
IR64607 A	WA	IRRI	98	100	7	32.0	1.3
IR66707 A	<i>O. perennis</i>	IRRI	100	100	3	31.0	1.4
PMS1 A	WA	India	100	100	7	35.5	1.9
PMS8 A	WA	India	100	100	7	41.5	1.7
PMS10 A	WA	India	100	100	7	46.0	1.8
Madhuri A	MS 577	India	95	100	7	32.0	1.6
Pragathi A	MS 577	India	97	100	7	39.5	1.7
Pushpa A	MS 577	India	95	100	7	35.0	1.7
Krishna A	WA	India	93	100	7	21.5	1.7
Krishna A	Kalinga I	India	100	100	7	29.7	1.6
CNTPR10 A	WA	Thailand	100	100	7	29.5	1.8
RD25 A	WA	Thailand	100	100	1	37.5	1.5
RD21 A	WA	Thailand	100	100	1	37.0	1.8
V20 A	WA	China	100	100	7	25.0	1.6

^aWA = wild abortive.

Table 2. Agronomic traits and disease reaction of CMS (A) and maintainer (B) lines. Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam. 1993 WS.

Line	Days to 50% flowering		Plant height (cm)		Panicles/plant (no.)		Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Grain shape ^a	Disease ^b reaction ^c
	A	B	A	B	A	B				
IR58025	81	84	68	85	11.2	6.0	21.0	72.0	LS	S
IR62829	72	72	68	77	16.6	8.2	15.8	49.0	LS	R
IR64608	73	73	69	80	11.0	6.0	17.0	82.0	M	S
IR67684	78	78	69	80	16.0	7.8	21.0	96.0	LS	S
IR64607	84	84	71	91	9.0	7.0	17.8	103.0	LS	MR
IR66707	81	81	71	91	12.5	6.8	17.8	99.6	LS	R
PMS1	87	83	73	85	12.0	7.6	19.6	95.0	LS	S
PMS8	83	79	66	84	17.0	11.0	27.0	113.0	LS	S
PMS10	83	83	65	86	13.0	5.0	23.6	126.0	LS	S
Madhuri	74	74	54	92	16.5	10.2	20.3	72.0	M	R
Pragathi	63	63	54	69	10.0	5.8	26.1	166.0	M	R
Pushpa	74	74	90	95	10.0	7.8	16.8	64.0	M	R
Krishna (WA)	67	67	57	76	13.0	9.8	16.6	48.0	M	S
Krishna (Kalinga)	63	63	54	69	13.0	9.2	19.3	36.6	M	S
CNTPR10	88	88	95	117	6.0	6.0	27.3	120.0	L	R
RD25	68	66	78	85	11.0	9.0	17.3	38.0	L	R
RD21	90	88	113	117	6.6	7.8	22.3	130.0	L	R
V20	62	62	61	73	15.5	8.6	19.0	72.0	M	S

^aLS = long slender, L = long, M = medium. ^bRagged stunt virus. ^cR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

A specific esterase band found in Annon-1S

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Isozymes have a noteworthy impact on regulating plant growth and development. To determine the specific proteins of isozymes in thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) rice, we performed vertical polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis at different plant growth stages.

Annon-1S is a natural mutant from indica line Annon-1. Its male sterility by environmental temperature is conditioned. Under high temperatures (daily mean > 26 °C), it has a stable sterile stage. The higher the temperature, the earlier the pollen development stage, which results in sterility. When temperature falls below the threshold, partial or normal fertility occurs. Studies indicate that a pair of recessive nuclear genes controls sterility and that segregating generations have goodness of fit to the Mendelian rules with respect to the trait.